

Perceptions of Dyslexia in Primary Education: A Study of Teachers in Rajasthan

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Abstract: Dyslexia is one of the most common learning disabilities. Dyslexia is still not well recognized and understood in the education sector, where teachers play a very important role in its early identification and timely interventions. This study was carried out to understand and examine the knowledge and misconceptions of primary school teachers in Rajasthan, India. This study was carried out with 135 private school teachers from Rajasthan, India. This study uses a structured questionnaire to examine the understanding of dyslexia in terms of definition, causes, symptoms, and interventions of dyslexia. The results indicate that most teachers (73%) recognized dyslexia as neurological disability and all (100%) understand dyslexia as reading related disorder, but there are still misconceptions that exist among the teachers. Nearly half (50%) of the teachers assume that dyslexia is curable by medicine, and nearly half (53%) of the teachers believe that dyslexia affects general intelligence. It is encouraging to note that most of the teachers (88%) acknowledged the importance of early identification of dyslexia. Teachers (97%) supported the idea of learning teaching methods that would reduce the difficulties and help a dyslexic child to learn better. The results highlight a critical gap between conceptual understanding of the illness and surface-level awareness about dyslexia among teachers.

Practical Implications: This field work find out the gap that points to the urgent need to equip teachers with the right teaching strategies, training, and continuous professional support to better understand the needs of dyslexic students. By doing so, teachers will be more prepared to identify and create inclusive classroom environments, which will support a dyslexic student's emotional and academic well-being.

Keywords: Dyslexia, Learning Disabilities; Pedagogy, Teachers' Perception, Rajasthan

1. Introduction

Dyslexia is one of the most common specific learning disabilities. Dyslexia affects children from all backgrounds and languages. It is characterized by difficulties with spelling, decoding, and accurate and fluent word recognition (Lyon,

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Shaywitz, & Shaywitz, 2003). According to research, 5–15% of school-age children worldwide display dyslexia symptoms, while many go undiagnosed (Shaywitz, 1998). Due to a lack of awareness about dyslexia, many dyslexic children in India complete their primary school years without the essential support (Karande & Kulkarni, 2005). Thus, early identification and appropriate interventions are crucial in reducing the emotional and academic difficulties faced by dyslexic students.

Teachers play a vital role in this situation. According to Aladwani and Al Shaye (2012), primary school teachers are often the first to notice a child's learning behaviors, reading difficulties, or indications of difficulty in class activities. While teachers are not required to diagnose dyslexia, their knowledge of its symptoms and their ability to recognize early warning indicators are essential for referral and additional assessment (Torgesen, 2000). A well-informed and aware teacher can make appropriate classroom changes for better learning, inform and guide parents to professional assistance, and provide the timely academic support required for a dyslexic child. On the other hand, teachers' ignorance could cause a dyslexic child's difficulties to be misinterpreted for laziness, carelessness, or a lack of intelligence (Hornstra et al., 2010). Thus, the classroom environment and the child's learning directly gets impacted on how teachers perceive dyslexia.

Research has shown that teachers' perception about dyslexia vary greatly around the globe. While some teachers have misconceptions, for example, that a child will "outgrow" the issue, as dyslexia is just about reversing letters, on the other hand, teachers are well aware of the condition and incorporate inclusive teaching practices in their classroom (Gwernan-Jones & Burden, 2010). In India, Teachers' perceptions and awareness are even more limited, particularly in states like Rajasthan, where access to specialized training and resources may be limited.

Primary education is where a child's academic journey begins. If dyslexia is not identified and treated during these years, children are likely to struggle with increasing academic difficulties, which could lead to poor performance, low self-esteem, and even dropout (Snowling & Hulme, 2012). Thus, early identification and teachers' willingness to support and accommodate students with learning disabilities in regular classroom settings are influenced by their attitudes (Glazzard, 2010).

The purpose of this study is to examine how primary teachers at private schools in Rajasthan perceive dyslexia. This study particularly focuses on their knowledge, awareness, and understanding of this specific learning disability. Teachers' opinions are very crucial in early identification of symptoms, informing and guiding parents to doctors for assessment, and all the emotional and academic support a child needs in the school, as teachers are students' first point of contact in the classroom. The study investigates how well teachers understand the characteristics of dyslexia, any misconceptions they might have, and the teaching methods they believe work best for helping dyslexic students. It also looks at the difficulties teachers face when dealing with dyslexic students in traditional classroom environments, such as the absence of official training, materials, and institutional support. By combining these observations, the study not only draws attention to the current knowledge and readiness gaps among teachers but also highlights the necessity of focused interventions, drives to raise awareness, and chances for professional growth for teachers.

The ultimate goal of this research is to equip the teaching community with the knowledge to identify and support dyslexic students, resulting in more inclusive and successful teaching methods. This study also highlights the significance of providing primary school teachers with appropriate information and resources. Raising awareness in Rajasthani primary schools can have a big impact on the academic performance and emotional well-being of children with dyslexia.

2. Literature Review

Dyslexia, from which 5-15% of school-aged children worldwide suffer, is widely recognized as one of the most common specific learning difficulties (Lyon, Shaywitz, & Shaywitz, 2003; Snowling, 2000). Even though it has a neurological cause, its symptoms, such as trouble with spelling, decoding, fluency, and accuracy of reading, can easily mislead teachers. Teachers are therefore very important for identifying early signs, sending students for the right assessment, and giving them the right academic support (Shaywitz, 1998; Torgesen, 2000). However, research consistently demonstrates that teachers' perceptions of dyslexia vary significantly based on context, with these variations often shaped by cultural attitudes towards learning difficulties, as well as by training and experience.

Various research has pointed out gaps in teachers' understanding of dyslexia. Aladwani and Al Shaye (2012) found that many Kuwaiti teachers knew what "dyslexia" was, but they didn't know much about its signs, causes, or treatments. It has been observed that elementary school teachers in India often have misconceptions regarding dyslexia, with some perceiving it as linked to laziness or insufficient effort. These misconceptions among teachers lead to delaying identification and promoting negative stereotypes (Glazzard, 2010; Gwernan-Jones & Burden, 2010). This can further negatively impact students' academic performance and self-esteem.

Teachers' perception of dyslexia has a great influence on how they respond to their students who have this learning disability. Hornstra et al. (2010) found that teachers with unfavorable attitudes or low expectations for dyslexic students

were less likely to give them challenging assignments, which in turn led to poor academic performance. On the other hand, teachers with favorable attitudes led to increased classroom inclusion and student motivation by challenging dyslexic children in the right direction. According to Karande and Kulkarni (2005), Children with learning disabilities are often classified as "slow learners" or "lazy" in the Indian context, which leads to their exclusion from regular classrooms.

Global research indicates that teacher preparation about dyslexia significantly enhances understanding and confidence in addressing dyslexia (Gwernan-Jones & Burden, 2010). For example, Snowling (2000) emphasized the necessity of preparing teachers with diagnostic knowledge and instructional strategies designed specifically for dyslexic students. Structured modules on learning disabilities are not often part of teacher training programs in India, and due to this disparity, numerous teachers may lack awareness of dyslexia or the pedagogical resources required to address it effectively.

While dyslexia has been extensively studied in Western contexts, very little research has been done in India. Cultural factors often impact how learning difficulties are perceived. For example, in Rajasthan and other regions of India, low academic achievement is not always attributed to particular cognitive challenges but rather to a lack of effort, family history, or socioeconomic limitations. According to Karande and Kulkarni (2005), this cultural perspective may make stigma worse and make early intervention more difficult. Therefore, creating culturally sensitive and practically implementable interventions requires an understanding of teachers' perceptions in regional contexts.

3. Methodology

This study adopted a mixed-methods approach to widely investigate primary teachers' perceptions and knowledge of dyslexia in private schools of Rajasthan. Methodology for this study integrates quantitative survey data with qualitative perceptions from interviews. The mixed-method research design allowed for a more complex understanding of teachers' awareness, misconceptions, and practical challenges in supporting dyslexic children (Makgato et al., 2022).

As part of quantitative research, a well-structured questionnaire was circulated to Rajasthan's primary school teachers. This questionnaire was aimed at measuring their understanding and attitudes regarding dyslexia. As part of qualitative research, semi-structured interviews were conducted to evaluate teachers' live classroom experiences, instructional approaches, and to identify training needs. By going beyond superficial awareness to capture the complexity of teachers' perceptions, this approach offered both breadth and depth to the primary research. The quantitative survey involved 135 primary school teachers from private schools in Rajasthan. The selection process was made to make sure that a variety of school settings were represented, which improved the findings' regional generalizability. A smaller sample of participants was interviewed for the qualitative phase. This was done to obtain more in-depth knowledge about classroom procedures and challenges that they face in the classroom if they encounter any student with special learning disability. The purpose of the questionnaire was to assess teachers' knowledge of dyslexia, including its definition and causes, neurological and genetic components, typical symptoms, successful teaching techniques, and common misconceptions (such as whether dyslexia is curable or related to intelligence).

Because the tool used a Likert-scale format, participants could indicate how much they agreed or disagreed with statements about inclusive education and dyslexia. To evaluate teachers' readiness and attitudes toward students with special education needs, this format has been used extensively

In addition to the survey, the semi-structured interviews gave teachers an opportunity to discuss their real-classroom experiences, like identifying dyslexic students, modifying their teaching methods as per dyslexic students' needs, and utilizing institutional support networks. These stories put the quantitative results in context and highlighted issues that a survey might miss. The survey was conducted both in-person and online to take into consideration the various accessibility levels across schools. Participation was completely voluntary, and confidentiality was assured to encourage honest responses.

This methodology made it possible to evaluate teachers' attitudes, practices, and knowledge regarding dyslexia. By combining both quantitative and qualitative methods, the study ensured that teachers' knowledge about dyslexia and real-life teaching experiences were documented. This type of comprehensive evaluation is essential to identify gaps in the current teacher education programs and direct targeted professional development interventions (Vaughn & Fletcher, 2021).

4. Findings and Analysis

The results of the study provide a valuable insight into the perceptions and understanding of dyslexia among private primary teachers of Rajasthan. Overall, despite teachers' awareness about dyslexia in some areas, there were still a lot of misconceptions. The findings revealed the gaps that might impact on how dyslexic students are identified and supported in classrooms.

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze quantitative data from the 135 primary teachers who completed questionnaires to identify teachers' knowledge and misconceptions. The analysis showed an accurate understanding of dyslexia and

the areas where misconceptions continued to exist. Thematic analysis of the qualitative data shows the needs, difficulties, and experiences of teachers. A complete picture of teacher perceptions was produced by combining these complementary analyses.

Almost all participants (100%) accurately identified dyslexia as a learning disorder that includes difficulty in reading and deciphering letters, words, and symbols. This demonstrates that most educators are aware of the basic definition of dyslexia. Misconceptions, however, emerged when questions concerning the connection between dyslexia and intelligence were posed. A significant misconception that could have an impact on how dyslexic students are viewed in terms of their academic potential is that, although 47% of respondents correctly stated that dyslexia does not affect general intelligence, the majority (53%) thought it did.

Another misconception about dyslexia is curability. While 72% of teachers mistakenly thought dyslexia could be "cured," only 28% of them correctly recognized that it cannot be cured by any medicine. In a similar way, only 37% of respondents correctly identified that dyslexia can be inherited, and 63% had false beliefs about its genetic foundation. More encouragingly, 73% of educators correctly recognized dyslexia as a neurological condition, although 27% were unsure of this basic fact.

When it came to differentiating dyslexia from general reading difficulties, teachers also made mistakes. Just 17% of the teachers responded correctly, while 83% believe that dyslexia affects all struggling readers. The role of medication was another area of misunderstanding: 50% of teachers thought that doctors could prescribe medication for dyslexia, even though there is no drug-based intervention or medical cure for the condition.

An encouraging finding is that 88% of teachers acknowledged that early identification can significantly reduce reading and writing errors in dyslexic students, which was promising. A small number of people (9%) still thought that dyslexia was a myth, but the vast majority (91%) did not agree that it is a problem that does not exist. This suggests that stigma is still present. Additionally, nearly all educators (97%) agreed that differentiated instruction and attention can help dyslexic students, showing that they are willing to change how they teach.

The long-term emotional and academic challenges that dyslexic students face were also acknowledged by many teachers. Approximately 77% of respondents correctly identified that dyslexic students often have low self-esteem and confidence throughout their lives, and 74% of respondents were aware that reading difficulties can persist in adulthood. These responses demonstrate that educators are aware of the broader emotional and psychological effects of dyslexia on young students.

These results give a mixed scenario about primary teachers' understanding of dyslexia (Figure 1) and (Figure 2). Although teachers have some accurate information, especially about the nature of dyslexia as a neurological learning disorder, and the value of early intervention. But teachers also have several misconceptions about it, including its impact on intelligence, curability, heredity, and the role of medication. These false beliefs have the potential to continue the stigma attached to dyslexia and hinder the effective classroom setup for dyslexic students. These findings highlight the urgent need for well-structured and organized teacher training programs that emphasize both the scientific knowledge of dyslexia and useful strategies for inclusive teaching methods for the classroom.

Figure 1: Teachers' Perception of Dyslexia

Figure 2: Teachers' Perception of Dyslexia (Practice & Impact)

5. Conclusions

The current research examined the attitudes, misconceptions, and knowledge about dyslexia of 135 private primary school teachers of Rajasthan. The results show a lack of agreement. It indicates that while teachers demonstrated an understanding of dyslexia as a real neurological learning disorder, there are still several deep-rooted misconceptions that may affect how they view and assist dyslexic students.

The results are also reassuring, as most of the teachers correctly identified dyslexia as a disorder that is not related to general intelligence. Most people agree that students with dyslexia need different kinds of learning experiences to succeed. Identifying their problems early and utilizing specialized teaching methods can help them make fewer mistakes when reading and writing. This indicates that teachers also want to help their students by using appropriate teaching methods that support everyone in their classroom. The results also have shown that teachers are aware of dyslexic students having emotional problems, like low self-esteem and confidence, and how this affects students' mental health outside of school.

The study has also found some alarming myths. Some teachers believed that dyslexia was genetic or that it could be "cured" or treated with medicine. Almost half of the teachers, on the other hand, thought that it affected the overall intelligence of the students. Teachers don't seem to know what makes dyslexia different from other learning problems. A considerable percentage of teachers also confused dyslexia with general reading difficulties, showing that there is a huge gap in understanding the distinctive traits of dyslexia in particular. These false beliefs may result in incorrect diagnoses, ineffective treatments, and, in certain situations, the stigmatization of students.

These results show how important it is to have targeted teacher education and training programs. Teachers are often the first to notice the signs of dyslexia, and how well they understand it directly affects the referral process, the way they teach, and the student's emotional health. If misconceptions persist, dyslexic students may be misinterpreted, abandoned, or unfairly labeled, which can worsen their academic and psychological well-being.

The study's conclusion highlights that increasing teachers' awareness of dyslexia involves more than just teaching facts; it also involves altering attitudes and behaviors to foster inclusive learning environments. Teachers can be empowered to play a critical role in early identification and intervention by addressing misconceptions through workshops, organized training, and ongoing professional development. Ultimately, increasing teachers' understanding of dyslexia not only improves educational outcomes for affected students but also fosters a more understanding and better learning environment.

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